

Agro-Tourism Development in Cambodia: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Agro-tourism, sometimes referred to as eco-tourism or rural tourism, has gained international acceptance as one of the primary methods for establishing rural sustainability. In this definition, agro-tourism refers to the fusion of agricultural, ecological, and cultural products for a variety of purposes, such as social, educational, recreational, health, and environmental. The agriculture industry is the main driver of the Cambodian economy, and in order to sustain the livelihoods and economics of the people living there, a number of tourism-related companies must expand. Finding the most crucial development methods for Cambodia's agro-tourism sector is the primary objective of this review. Aspects of political stability, the development of rural community infrastructure, strategy plans, tourist product stability, marketing components, information system components, encouraging local tourism, investment appeal, and financial support are among the main essential considerations. Strategies are essential to expeditiously enhancing the agro-tourist activities delineated in government policies, including those pertaining to the agricultural sector, agricultural communities, and nature, culture, and society-related tourism. The review has revealed that a wide range of factors could greatly aid in the adoption of agro-tourism development plans and methodologies throughout Cambodia's diverse ecological zones.

INTRODUCTION

Agro-tourism, sometimes referred to as eco-tourism or rural tourism, is acknowledged by many countries as one of the primary rural policies that support rural sustainability. According to our definition, agro-tourism is a subset of eco-, agricultural, and cultural products that are used for social, cultural, educational, recreational, restorative, and environmental objectives. Through agro-tourism, we can rediscover the significance of rural resources that were disregarded when a nation underwent economic modernity. It also gives farmers and policymakers a chance to see rural development from a different perspective than the one that was previously dominated by the agricultural product industry. Ohe (2006). Agrotourism, on the other hand, is the combination of tourism and agriculture. It involves tourists visiting agricultural regions and participating in agricultural activities such as planting, harvesting, fishing, and so forth while they travel for leisure, to relax, to spend time and money on happiness and enjoyment (Reynolds, 2005). Although the term "agro-tourism" has many diverse meanings and applications, it often refers to the production of agricultural products, rural living, and the preservation of the rural environment for the benefit of both urban and rural visitors. (Ohe, 2006; Liu, 2006; Kannan and Singh, 2006; Page and Getz, 1997). In Cambodia, agriculture is the primary industry. The majority of people in Cambodia are farmers, with rice being the primary crop grown in each of the country's several agro-ecological zones. Planting rice is the main usage of the area. For improved Cambodian economics and lives, there are too many natural tourist, cultural tourism, and social tourism forms that need to grow. The review article's goal is to identify a plan for growing Cambodia's agrotourism industry.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Agro-tourism has been characterized in a variety of ways by numerous scholars. To put it simply, agro-tourism is defined as "the act of seeing an operating farm or any related to agriculture, horticultural, or agricultural businesses operation for the aim of enjoyment, education, or active participation in the farm operation" (Lobo, n.d.). "Any farming operation that serves directly to customers in general with retail sales and/or offering of services, including food, fiber, flowers, shrubs, trees, and other agricultural goods and running marketing at the production location" is another way to describe agro-tourism (Che et al., 2015). Agrotourism-related activities have the ability to produce extra income needed to sustain small and medium-sized farming businesses as well as rural communities. It may be promoted as an opportunity for both tourists and residents to get up close and personal with the environment and agriculture. Better public engagement with local farms and ranches can promote a heightened awareness and respect for the working landscapes that sustain and protect natural resources. Maintaining the quality of the environment based on nature, which includes productive agriculture, is necessary to sustain agrotourism in the future. 2017; University of California. The term mainly focuses on various agricultural products and practices that include agrotourism. Kizos and Iosifides (2007) provide an additional definition of agro-tourism that includes additional details: "Tourist actions of small scale,

household or cooperative in background, being established in countryside regions by people that work in agriculture."

Nonetheless, a number of guides also highlight agro-tourism as a possible substitute industry that utilizes agricultural resources. According to Maetzold (2002), agro-tourism is an alternative industry that connects with value-added or unusual agricultural products and marketing. Then, a grower or rancher can take part in a number of other ventures to boost their entrepreneurial income share. This idea has been used to discover a new market niche and commercial opportunity in agrotourism.

Therefore, Virginia Low defines agro-tourism as "any activity conducted on a farm or ranch that permits members of the general public to view or enjoy the countryside activities, involving agriculture, ranching, historic, societal, natural activities and attractions, or harvest-your-own activities, for entertainment, for recreational use, or educational purposes." (Schilling and colleagues, 2006).

The distinctions between agro-tourism and mass tourism, as well as the significance of a solitary or small-group approach, have been highlighted in most classifications. Sustainability is another objective of the agro-tourism idea, in addition to the agricultural community's economic, cultural, and environmental well-being. Nevertheless, agro-tourism activities provide visitors with an opportunity to partake in leisure and educational pursuits associated with farming, rural, natural, and cultural attractions, as per the previously described definitions. They also provide farmers with an opportunity to share their experiences and market their products. Moreover, agro-tourism is described as a cross between the tourism and agriculture sectors, which work together to generate new, profitable markets for agricultural products and services as well as lodging options for tourists staying in nearby towns. Most of the many approaches to tourism have a direct bearing on the rural economy and, by extension, on rural development. This is the main reason why rural regions are emphasized as tourist destinations in different tourism approaches. Therefore, agro-tourism creates new business chances for rural areas as well as the country's macroeconomics by replacing traditional tourism (Mahaliyanaarachchi, 2015).

In any case, tourism is a process that involves society, the economy, and the natural environment. Mass tourism, the most popular type of travel, is typified by significant spatial and economic inequality, with the industry's detrimental effects on the environment and culture spreading broadly while its positive effects on the economy are relatively small (Williams, 1997). When searching for consumable goods and services, mass travelers make sure that their desire to relax throughout their trip is not compromised. But the people here see tourism, especially mass tourism, as both a problem and an opportunity. The problems stem from how tourism affects the environment, local culture, and society; the opportunities come from the jobs and revenue it brings in. (Tsartas, 2003). Agrotourism, according to Reynolds (2005), is the term for businesses owned and operated by farmers that engage in agricultural activities for the entertainment and education of visitors. Moreover,

agrotourism shows promise in increasing farm income and profitability. A small percentage of rural tourism and agricultural practices worldwide include agrotourism, with the notable exception of certain European countries, such as Austria, France, Italy, and Switzerland, where an astonishing number of farms offer some form of tourism. A significant amount of rural tourism in several countries and regions is derived from agrotourism (Junaedi and Utama, 2016).

METHODOLOGY

This article is based on literature research study. The sources of the data are books, publications, policies and regulations, and journal articles. As part of the process of gathering data, it is possible to identify, obtain, and examine the previously stated written documents. Studying books or e-books, research databases, reputable institution websites, online media websites, and reading books can all be used to find facts. Organizing the data, reading, defining, describing, and making conclusions are the processes in the data analysis technique.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Agricultural Development in Cambodia

The National Strategic Development Plan for Cambodia, 2019–2023, was created to put the Rectangular Strategy in practice. One of the plan's top focuses is to promote the agricultural, natural resources, and rural development (ANRRD) sector. The ANRRD objectives may be found at the highest level of policy and planning, known as the Rectangular Strategy. ANRRD sector growth of 5% annually is the target. Increased productivity, crop diversity, and commercialization are the objectives of sector development. Strengthening a range of agricultural services (including agricultural extension and information provision), promoting good agricultural practices, promoting mechanization, improving land use management, promoting higher technology, and advocating for more resilient livestock and fisheries practices are all part of the new Rectangular Strategy (Phase IV). Additionally, developing agribusiness networks and strengthening agricultural cooperatives are also important aspects of this phase.

The MAFF's Agricultural Sector Strategic Development Plan, 2019–2023 addresses the following points in order to support the goals of the National Strategic Development Plan, 2019–2023: (i) improving agricultural productivity, diversification, and commercialization; (ii) promoting animal health and production; (iii) managing fisheries and developing aquaculture; (iv) managing and developing sustainable forestry and wildlife resources; and (v) enhancing the effectiveness of support services and human resource development.¹³⁷ A master plan for agriculture sector development toward 2030, a strategic planning document for livestock development to 2024, and a Strategic Planning Framework for Fisheries, 2010–2019 are only a few of the agriculture subsector planning papers that are available. By moving from the informal export of paddy rice to the formal export of milled rice, the Policy Document on the Promotion of Paddy Production and Export of Milled Rice, often known as the

rice policy, seeks to establish Cambodia as a globally recognized milled rice exporter (ADB, 2021).

In five areas—management and development of water resources, management of flood and drought, protection and conservation of water resources, management of information on water resources and meteorology, and improvement of administrative management and human resources development—the Ministry of Water Resources and Meteorology (MOWRAM) has outlined strategies and targets for water resources management in its Strategic Development Plan for Water Resources and Meteorology, 2019–2023. The National Water Resources Management and Sustainable Irrigation Road Map and Investment Program, 2019–2033, created by MOWRAM in 2019, outlines the key initiatives to be carried out during the following 15 years. The program promotes (i) sustainable water resources management, (ii) complete irrigation schemes, (iii) self-sustaining O&M of irrigation systems, and (iv) profitable irrigated agriculture with the goal of achieving a whole-of-system approach in water resources management and irrigation development (ADB, 2021).

Plan for Agricultural Sector Strategy

Minimal Handling and Processing After Harvest

About 10% of all agricultural output in Cambodia is processed domestically, while only 8% of all official exports by value are processed agricultural exports. The agro-processing industry is mainly undeveloped, with the exception of rice milling (with its increased capacity) and simple processing of pepper and rubber. If Cambodia wants to capitalize on the economic prospects that result from adding value to its agricultural goods, private investment is required in postharvest handling and processing. The affordability and dependability of energy, unofficial fees for licenses and paperwork, a lack of knowledge and expertise, challenges securing development funding, and access to equipment and technology are the main obstacles to increasing agro-processing in Cambodia (ADB, 2021).

Availability of Agricultural Equipment and Inputs

Mechanization and high-quality agricultural inputs are necessary for modernizing agriculture and raising worker productivity for farm production. The availability of improved seed varieties is restricted in Cambodia. In 2019, the annual supply of high-quality rice seeds has been growing, but it still only accounted for 20% of the demand. All vegetable seeds, with the exception of those grown at government research facilities, are imported. The 2008 Seed Law contains a seed policy with seed quality criteria, however the government of Cambodia has not yet approved it. Furthermore, it still needs to develop the necessary guidelines and checks and balances to bring the seed law into compliance. From 10.0 kilograms per hectare of agriculture in 2005 to 33.0 kilograms in 2018, Cambodia used more fertilizer. The usage of pesticides has increased, particularly in the vegetable industry and during the dry season when rice is grown. Pesticides are also imported, but most of them are said to

be either inadequately or not at all regulated. It's critical to utilize controlled pesticides correctly for the safety of farmers, food safety, and ecosystem health. Agriculture in Cambodia has gradually become more mechanized, with equipment like water pumps and power tillers taking the role of human labor. In order to meet income prospects outside of farming, further mechanization is anticipated to boost worker productivity and farming earnings (ADB, 2021).

Market Accessibility, Transportation, and Logistics

Farmers are predominantly price takers. Most sell their crops to traders just after harvest. Varieties are mixed and only small volumes of pure varieties are found, which hinder value recognition and addition. For further value addition in agriculture, access to international markets is increasingly important. Efficient transport and logistic infrastructure and services are necessary to strengthen agri-food value chains. Roads are the major means of domestic transport in Cambodia. Cambodia's domestic transport costs have been reduced, but they remain higher than neighboring countries such as Thailand and Viet Nam. Road improvements and increased competition among local transport services are needed to reduce transport costs. Similarly, Cambodia's physical market infrastructure is outdated, congested, unsanitary, and requires significant improvement. There is also no reliable cold chain system in place to ensure the proper handling and safe storage and distribution of perishable agricultural and food products (ADB, 2021).

Technology for Information and Communication Accessibility

To promote digital growth, the government has lately put in place a number of policy initiatives, including the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Masterplan 2020 and the draft Cambodia e-Government Master Plan, 2017-2022. However, the country is still lagging behind in terms of digital penetration and technological readiness. ICT may play a major role in facilitating the connections between the various stakeholders in the agriculture value chain, such as farmers, agribusiness owners, consumers, and government agencies. Value chain platforms that enable participants to exchange commodities, services, and information will be simpler to establish as a result of information digitalization (ADB, 2021).

Financial Accessibility

Despite increased funding availability in rural regions, the primary barrier for Cambodian farmers and agribusinesses continues to be access to capital. In 2018, the total amount of formal finance in Cambodia that was attributed to agriculture and agribusinesses was only 9.4%. Numerous issues, such as high collateral requirements, high rate short-term loans, a lack of credit history, and insufficient financial literacy, can be blamed for their poor financial access. Furthermore, there seem to be signs that the COVID-19 pandemic has restricted access to credit and funding. It will be crucial to address the restricted access to funding in order to support post-pandemic recovery (ADB, 2021).

Cooperatives and Extension Services

Although around 70% of all villages have access to public or private extension services, these services are frequently supply-driven and generic in character. The government is reorganizing its extension services to be more diverse, demand-driven, and decentralized in order to promote agricultural diversification and increase outreach. Improving government extension services requires close cooperation with extension services through donor-funded programs and the participation of private service providers. The government assists farmer cooperatives to get access to economies of scale in production and marketing agreements. In 2019, there were over 1,200 registered cooperatives, despite the fact that their capacities differ. Farmer cooperatives and other farmer organizations need to be reinforced considerably more if the nation's farming sector is to grow sustainably (ADB, 2021).

Figure 1. Growth in Gross Domestic Product (Agriculture), 2000-2020
 Source: Asian Development Bank, 2021.

Tourism Development in Cambodia: Siem Reap Tourism Development Strategy 2021-2035

A Plan For Creating Priority Tourist Areas

To fulfill the vision of tourist growth in Siem Reap 2021-2035, the master plan sets out proposals for the construction and development of 06 priority tourism zones: The following are the top tourist destinations in Cambodia: 1. Jayavarman-Norodom "Phnom Kulen" National Park; 2. The environs of Banteay Srey protected area; 3. Angkor Heritage site; 4. Siem Reap city; 5. Tonle Sap Lake area; and 6. New Siem Reap tourism site. In addition to cultural heritage, natural heritage will be essential to the growth of highly competitive, sustainable tourism, and the master plan will encourage the development of this kind of tourism in Siem Reap, including ecotourism, adventure tourism, and natural tourism. Many tourist locations, like street natural sceneries and

natural tourism communities, offer this kind of tourism activity; nevertheless, it also necessitates development requirements in those regions. Development of natural and ecotourism sites can be located in northern (Phnom Kulen National Park) and southern (Tonle Sap Lake) areas of Siem Reap, as well as rural areas that can leverage the potential of natural resources to develop new tourist destinations in response to the growth of tourists' demand (RGC, 2021).

A Plan for Creating New Tourism Products

Products pertaining to culture, heritage, religion, and belief: In order to effectively utilize the resources of its cultural legacy for tourism benefits, Siem Reap will need to develop new products for the cultural tourism industry and reposition itself in relation to what already exists. In order to provide appealing travel products, the creative sector must also be expanded by drawing in and making use of the talent of writers, artists, actors, dancers, and painters. Thus, in order to elevate Siem Reap to the status of the world's preeminent cultural tourism destination, extend the duration of visitor stays, and augment visitor expenditures, the subsequent measures had to be contemplated: The first action is to create a global heritage circuit and trail; the second is to establish a museum of civilization; the third is to develop innovative tourism that connects with the creative industry. Action 4: Develop and enhance visitor interpretive tools for cultural heritage (RGC, 2021).

Green Tourism Goods

Due to the existing high volume of international visitors and the growing number of Cambodian visitors, the master plan prioritizes the development of green tourism in Siem Reap. "Green tourism" is something that visitors to Siem Reap and the surrounding areas are really interested in (RGC, 2021). Stakeholder participation in creation, management, and commercial operations are critical components of the success of Siem Reap's green tourism initiative. The aim of this participation is not limited to leaders or strategy developers; it also includes tourism service providers, development partners, local residents, and environmentally conscious tourists. Currently, if tourism is not properly managed, it can damage four major issues: waste, water, electricity, and biodiversity. Green tourism helps to address these difficulties. In order to overcome these obstacles, the following needs to be done: The first action is to promote ecotourism and community-based tourism. The second is to make Siem Reap into an environmentally friendly city by organizing contests for "Clean City, Clean Resort, Good Service, Best Hospitality." Take Action 3) Developing a "Tourist Park" and improving the "One Tourist One Tree" initiative Take Action 4) Putting the ASEAN and Cambodia Green Standards into practice in the tourism sector (RGC, 2021).

MICE Tourism Products

Siem Reap is ideal for the development of tourism offerings centered around gatherings, conferences, and events that can draw a wider range of domestic and foreign visitors and lengthen their stays. Currently, organizing tourism events is essential to making Siem Reap tourism more competitive.

These tourism products can be arranged as local, regional, or international events. Examples of these events include: 1) sporadic events, like hosting major international conferences or sporting events that take place in different countries each year; 2) yearly regular events, like Angkor Sangkranta, International Culture Festival, Music Festival, Food Festival, Sports Competition, etc. In order to qualify as a MICE destination, Siem Reap needs to take the following steps: Action 1: Planning one-time events; Action 2: Planning ongoing activities Third Action: Establishing the MICE tourism goods' supporting infrastructure (RGC, 2021).

Products for Agrotourism and Rural Tourism

Increasing the options available to both domestic and foreign travelers is the goal of developing agrotourism and rural tourism in Siem Reap through the following initiatives: The first action is to integrate the Rural Development Strategy and Action Plan. The second action is to modernize and diversify agrotourism and rural tourist goods. Step 3: Guaranteeing the caliber of agrotourism and rural tourism offerings, Step 4: Increasing visitor awareness Action 5: Encouraging local communities to participate Action 6: Create a fund for agrotourism and rural tourism (RGC, 2021).

Products for Sports Tourism

Products for sports tourism play a significant role in Siem Reap's tourism diversification strategy. In terms of outdoor sports tourism, Siem Reap has a lot of promise, particularly for the half marathon event. In order to implement this strategy, the following measures need to be considered: First action: organizing more appealing sporting events. Action 2: Creating a variety of sports tourist offerings. Action 3: Developing and promoting tourism for indoor sports (RGC, 2021).

Travel Products for Seniors, Health, and Retirees: Developing senior tourism in conjunction with the health Tourism Development Master Plan in Siem Reap 2021-2035, 64 tourist and second home tourism, as well as cultural heritage tourism and ecotourism tourism, is a common approach outlined for these sectors in Siem Reap. In order to make this happen, the following needs to be done: Creating imaginative study excursions for elderly travelers is the first action. Action 2: Creating senior travel experiences in Siem Reap Step 3: Encouraging elderly travelers (RGC, 2021).

Tourist Attraction and Promotion Strategy

Identifying Important Sources for the Tourism Market

Siem Reap must also think about how to draw in both the current and future targeted markets. As a result, the following measures must be taken: Action 1: Drawing in large foreign travel markets; Action 2: Encouraging and drawing in domestic travel markets (RGC, 2021).

Different Strategies to Advance Tourism in Siem Reap

The following steps must be taken in order to boost Siem Reap's tourism promotion: Action 1: Researching and creating institutional frameworks to support tourism in Siem Reap. Action 2: Planning study trips to Siem Reap and boosting attendance at tourism exhibits and significant international events. Action 3: Researching the creation of the Provincial Convention Center in Siem Reap and aiding in the marketing of MICE travel. Action 4: Encouraging investment in upscale travel goods in Siem Reap. Action 5: bolstering the route for disseminating tourism-related information. Action 6: Increase the amount of materials and documentation promoting travel that are published in Chinese, English, French, Korean, and Japanese. Action 7: Increasing the destinations in Siem Reap's competitive advantage. Action 8: Increasing the scope of the partnership with renowned national and worldwide media outlets, newspapers, and magazines. Action 9: Using Digital Technology to Promote Tourism in Siem Reap More Effectively (Digital Marketing). Action 10: Researching the development of a tourism branding strategy for the province of Siem Reap's main tourist destinations, utilizing and promoting "Cambodia: The Kingdom of Wonder-Feel the Warmth" (RGC, 2021).

A Plan to Improve the Tourism Industry's Sustainability and Quality

Enhancing the Standard of Tourism

Three methods serve as the foundation for strategies aimed at raising the standard of Siem Reap's tourism services: (1) Increasing quality through green standards in the tourism sector in compliance with ASEAN and Cambodian standards; (2) Increasing quality through rating systems; and (3) Increasing quality through the implementation of laws and regulations. In order to execute this strategy, the following steps need to be taken: 1) Improving the standard of lodging and hotel services in Siem Reap, 2) Improving the standard of dining establishments, 3) Improving the standard of Siem Reap's adult entertainment venues, 4) Improving the caliber of travel agencies and tour operators in Siem Reap, 5) Improving the caliber of tour guides, 6) Improving the standard of Siem Reap's gift shops, 7 and 8) focus on enhancing Siem Reap's reputation as a safe travel destination and bolstering the industry's ability to withstand emergencies, diseases that spread quickly, and natural calamities (RGC, 2021).

Development of Human Resources in the Tourism Industry

Even though Siem Reap is home to a large number of tourism vocational schools and training institutions that offer vocational training in hospitality, food production, management, communication, foreign language, and tour guiding, the training still falls short of the demands of the city's tourism labor market, which is rapidly expanding annually as a result of the mismatch between the supply and demand of professional workers. The majority of staff members have gotten peer-to-peer training instead of official training, and there are still not enough training facilities, particularly at Siem Reap's tourism vocational institutions. Only 43% of workers in the tourism sector, according to the survey, have professional training and are acknowledged by the Ministry of Labor and Vocational Training or the Ministry of Tourism. Furthermore, the

bulk of workers (only 55%) have completed professional training, but management level training is quite extensive (up to 60%) and intermediate level training is scarce (still missing from 90% of the workforce). According to RGC (2021), the required staffing ratio is 75% for professional personnel, 20% for middle management or supervisors, and 5% for senior management.

In the meantime, there is a greater need for human resources in this industry due to the increase in visitor arrivals in Siem Reap. About 640,000 tourism workers will be needed in Siem Reap by 2030, and 940,000 by 2035, according to the forecast. Of these, 53% will work in hotels and other lodging, 7% in food services, 7% in tour operators and travel agencies, 2% in tour guide services, 6% in adult entertainment center services, 6% in community-based tourism, and 20% in ecotourism and other tourism-related businesses. As a result, the strategic plan for Siem Reap's human resource development in the tourism industry should concentrate on basic and intermediate tourism vocational training by increasing the number of newly skilled workers and enhancing their ability to acquire professional skills and be recognized under the ASEAN and national qualification frameworks. In order to execute this strategy, the following steps need to be taken: Action 1: Expanding the availability of tourism-related vocational training. Action 2: Organizing and fortifying Siem Reap's system of professional growth in tourism training. Action 3: Making the training on creative thinking, entrepreneurship, and new start-ups in tourism stronger. Action 4: Improving the standard of tour guide education in Siem Reap and the neighboring areas. Action 5: Encouraging tourism workers in Siem Reap to register more firmly with the National Social Security Fund (RGC, 2021).

Boosting the Local Economy with the Growth of Tourism

The connection between the growth of tourism and the goods and services generated and offered by locals, farmers, artisans, traders, and other economic actors is what makes tourism a stronger force in the community. To guarantee that locals enjoy shared and inclusive prosperity, it is crucial to strategically enhance the relationship between tourism, agriculture, and the creative sectors. In order to guarantee the supply and increase consumption of locally produced goods that will significantly contribute to the creation of value-added, the creation of job opportunities, and the reduction of poverty, Siem Reap must expand the green belt surrounding its cities, towns, and tourist attractions through the cultivation of crops, livestock farming, aquaculture, and the promotion of handicrafts and small and medium-sized businesses. Locals and farmers in the Siem Reap area are currently engaged in new business-oriented activities, such as: 1) Agriculture Diversification: this involves transforming traditional livestock farming, aquaculture, and vegetable and fruit cultivation into new products with high yields, quality, safety, and high value-added for tourism (allowing the creation of a green belt); 2) Handicraft and souvenir products serve as an additional source of income. The local agricultural sector has not yet completely realized the potential of supply to the tourism sector (particularly, hotels and restaurants), as a result of the

inadequate variety of local agricultural goods in terms of quality and logistics. For the tourism sector in Siem Reap, several handicrafts and mementos are imported from nearby nations or other provinces. Consequently, the master plan asks for boosting the quality and output of mementos for the tourism industry in addition to implementing agricultural diversification linked to tourism. As per the findings of the 2019 Tourists and Tourism Businesses Survey, local products are utilized by tourism facilities to the tune of only 42.7%. Souvenirs: Handicrafts and clothing accounted for about 46% and 36% of the purchases made by foreign visitors, respectively (RGC, 2021).

The following procedures need to be taken in order to produce tourism goods that strengthen Siem Reap's local economy: 1) Expanding the agricultural sector to attract tourists; 2) Crafts and mementos should be developed into high-quality "Products made in Cambodia" (RGC, 2021).

Environment Management Strategy

Solid Waste Management

We can reduce the strain on resource recovery and landfilling by converting garbage into electricity. For this reason, the new solid waste management system for Siem Reap intends to increase the chain of technical systems' efficacy in solid waste management. These systems rely on the use of treatment and recycling technologies, institutional processes of solid waste management in Siem Reap, and the "4R" principles. Therefore, it is necessary to adhere to the following protocols for Siem Reap's solid waste management: The actions include developing a solid waste management system, building a financial system to protect the environment, and supporting the Siem Reap contest movement for "Clean City, Clean Resort, Clean Service, and Best Hospitality." Digital technology is also being used in solid waste management. RGC (2021).

Promoting Natural Areas

As per the "Clean City" requirement, green area management plays a vital role in upholding an environmentally clean atmosphere. Important steps to support green spaces include developing a tourism park and improving the gardens in Siem Reap. For this strategy's promotion of green areas to be successful, the following actions must be taken: Among the projects include beautifying the gardens, safeguarding the big tree, and establishing a "Tourist Park" in Siem Reap City. RGC (2021).

Preserving Natural Ecosystems

We must collaborate to improve the preservation of the environment and natural resources in order to support the future expansion of tourism in Siem Reap. Of particular importance is the preservation of natural ecosystems in the city's most well-known tourist attractions, such as Tonle Sap Lake. To ensure the sustainability of natural ecosystems, the following actions must be taken into account: The steps taken include strengthening and expanding the roles, duties, and responsibilities of the provincial administration on the management, conservation, and protection of floodplain and flooded forests, as

well as creating an inter-institutional mechanism to coordinate, safeguard, and address the issues facing natural ecosystems, particularly in the Tonle Sap Lake region (RGC, 2021).

A Plan for Building Infrastructure and Improving Connectivity to Promote Tourism.

In order to enhance connectivity, Siem Reap's tourism sector has to expand in lockstep with infrastructure development by 2035. Siem Reap's present infrastructure, which is connected by land, sea, and air, makes it a very attractive destination for tourists and investors. The following are the strategies and plans for enhancing Siem Reap's infrastructure and connections to facilitate the city's expansion as a tourism destination between 2021 and 2035. Promote internal and worldwide connectivity: For the purpose of supporting the city's tourism development in line with the previously described goal, the master plan must consider promoting both internal and external connectivity to Siem Reap (RGC, 2021).

Maximize the Improvement of the Tourism-Related Infrastructure: Water, electricity, and telecommunications/internet services are among the infrastructures that sustain Siem Reap and the tourism sector in Cambodia, and their continued development is crucial to the city's tourism economy. In order to create places worthy of being designated as "Tourist Routes," action plans call for building clean water and electricity infrastructure, enhancing broadband internet and communications services for tourism in Siem Reap, and strengthening road infrastructure (RGC, 2021).

Agro-tourism Development in Cambodia

These approaches are intended to maximize the potential of rural settings so that tourists, both domestic and foreign, can take advantage of new opportunities for "seeing" and "doing" throughout their tour. The expansion of tourism has the potential to improve societal structure (Lankford, 1994). The primary criteria used to identify agro-tourism destinations are local interest, homogeneity or heterogeneity, visitor cardinality, and the level of development of tourism sites. Several investigations have been carried out in the domain of tourism and hospitality studies to assess the level of contentment among guests. For example, research on visitor satisfaction has been carried out by Yuksel (2001), Ryan and Cessford (2003), and Bowen and Clarke (2002). The natural environment and its quality can either support or contradict tourism-related activities because tourism takes place in a certain location.

Accommodations, tourist destination attractiveness, environmental factors, sociocultural factors, offer elements, infrastructure facilities, political stability, community involvement in tourism, aspects of advancement, marketing, and information systems are some of the fundamental factors that determine a destination's attractiveness and its potential for growth as an agri-tourism destination. It consists of three parts: food, entertainment, and lodging (Khanal & Shrestha, 2019). The objective of this growth in rural tourism is to

diversify the industry in order to facilitate the coexistence of newly developed and current tourism offerings.

Increasing the options available to both domestic and foreign travelers is the goal of developing agro-tourism and rural tourism. To this end, the following initiatives will be put into practice:

1. **Political stability:** The dangerous conditions for their travels are a major concern for all of the tourists. Travelers feel comfortable and secure when there is political stability. The democratic peace theory states that democracy will lead to political stability. Political stability in a country is linked to security and safety. When safety and security are threatened, war will be waged to eventually restore them. When planning a trip or vacation, tourists' primary concerns are safety and protection (Ingram et al., 2013).
2. **Infrastructure development in the country:** Transportation in Cambodia is facilitated by the network of air, rail, water, and land links. Land transportation is most common in Cambodia. There are about 4,235 kilometers of national roads and 3,675 kilometers of provincial roads. Many travel agencies transport tourists with busses and autos (Chheang, 2015). In order to connect visitors to the rural areas, the agro-tourism sector has to establish land roads.

Rail links exist between Phnom Penh and Kompong Chhnang, Pursat, Battambang, Sisophon, and Poipet. Due to the low quality and service, very few tourists travel the 386-kilometer route from Phnom Penh to Sisophon-Poipet and the 264-kilometer route from Phnom Penh to Kep-Sihanoukville (Chheang, 2015).

In Cambodia, there are three distinct waterway systems: the Tonle Sap, the Mekong River, and the waterways near the gulf. In addition, there are tour boats that take tourists to see the Great Lake and 17 other neighboring islands, as well as some waterway transportation firms that carry tourists between Phnom Penh and Siem Reap via Tonle Sap, the Great Lake (Chheang, 2015).

There are two major international airports in Phnom Penh and Siem Reap, as well as two smaller airports: Kong Keng in Sihanouk Town and Ratanakiri in Ratanakiri Province. Thirteen domestic air companies and fourteen foreign flight companies operate. The majority of guests arrive by plane. The main providers of domestic transportation are tour and travel agencies, which provide service of a respectable caliber at competitive rates (Chheang, 2015). The airport is very important for foreign visitors to Cambodia.

The government should be spending on infrastructure development in the tourism sector and promoting private investment in the construction of tourism amenities, for instance, designate and modify tourism locations as satellite sites surrounding each hub, such as hotels, cable cars, amusement parks, etc.; conduct awareness programs concerning the preservation and protection of women's and marginalized groups' intellectual works (Khanal & Shrestha, 2019).

Integrating the Rural Development Strategy and Action Plan

The strategy and implementation plan for rural development must take into account the growth of agrotourism and rural tourism. To carry out this strategic effort, the organizations in the tourist, infrastructure, rural development and agriculture, education, etc. sectors must collaborate closely. To accomplish the goals of both local and national economic growth as well as poverty reduction, the development of rural tourism requires the formation of an interministerial team under the National Committee for the Development of Tourism. The development of agrotourism and rural tourism is coordinated by the Provincial Office Tourism Development Committee. We need the support of NGOs in the interim, and the corporate sector needs to be represented in this interministerial working group (rural tourism and agrotourism associations should be founded). To ensure the expansion of this industry, knowledge and technology transfers are required for the design and development of tourism goods that support rural and agrotourism (RGC, 2021).

Ensuring the Quality of Rural and Agrotourism

Putting in place quality standards that satisfy the following criteria for both agrotourism and rural tourism in order to ensure the standard of these goods: 1) Situations: preservation of the commercial buildings and presentation of hygienic practices; 2) Physical and personal comfort: the standard of tourism services and the hygiene of service staff; 3) Hospitality and service: providing customers with excellent services; 4) A Focus on the Tourist Experience: the development of authentic activities that elevate visitors' experiences, maintain standards, and handle each customer equally and impartially; 5) Offers ease and options to tourists: providing options will enhance visitors' experiences; 6) Tidiness and 7) Label creation: transit through rural areas (RGC, 2021).

Improving and Broadening the Selection of Agrotourism Experiences:

A recreational region that offers educational tours, special interest tours for photographers, farm and village excursions, and other activities is known as an agro-tourism zone. Furthermore, travellers are increasingly using technology to get information. It is possible to meet the expectations of both current and future customers and enhance the engagement of rural tourism products by implementing innovative approaches of interpretation. The development and management of rural and agrotourism in Cambodia also depend on technology. RGC (2021). By reducing negative environmental effects, increasing local ownership, community projects, job opportunities, independence, and economic gains through the application of sustainable development guidelines in the tourism industry, and fortifying the links between agro-tourism and other economic sectors, Nepal was able to increase its product offerings (Khanal & Shrestha, 2019).

Raising Awareness Among Guests

In order to raise awareness among tourists, the following steps must be taken: 1) adding a section on agro-tourism and agricultural tourism to

Cambodia Tourism's official website; 2) improving the Tourist Instructions Book and increasing the amount of information connected to tourism on social media; 3) organizing a familiarization trip for the media, including bloggers; 4) Associating with travel agencies that function in remote regions; 5) developing smartphone applications for self-driving tours to rural and agrotourism locations; 6) Establishing and creating post-visit reward programs, such as experience-sharing groups on WeChat, Facebook, or WhatsApp, in order to encourage people to return and spread the word about new agro-tourism services; and 7) Using "Rural Agro-tourism," an event co-hosted by the Ministry of Rural Development and the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries, to develop a well-targeted tourism marketing strategy with the aim of promoting agricultural activities and elevating the area as a destination for both rural and agro-tourism (RGC, 2021). Internet marketing will be used to promote Nepal in the global origin market, in addition to the creation of its tourism label and other sub-brands (Khanal & Shrestha, 2019). Promoting Blimbingsari Tourism Village in Bali with Incentive Travel. Tourists are strongly encouraged to visit the small town of Blimbingsari for the following reasons: physical training, intellectual stimulation, rest and relaxation, stress relief, family and friend visits, escape from daily routines, discovery of new things, and travel to new places (Junaedi and Utama, 2016). In time being, there will be events at the villages' popular tourist spots, providing guests with experiences like discovering the customs and skills of the region in addition to engaging and educational programs (RGC, 2021).

Encouraging Local Communities to Participate

Building capacity and providing training should be used to involve local communities in the following activities: 1) Developing business plans (forming a manual for rural businesses); 2) Raising digital literacy for online marketing, customerservice, and community-based tourism (for reservations); 3) Producing high-caliber travel products; and 4) Acquiring sustainable financial management (RGC, 2021). Folk traditions and customs should be promoted and preserved in conformity with popular preferences. Together, these three elements generate the standard services and goods for agro-tourism, which should ideally be paired with some elements of modern tourism programs targeted at the urban market (Yang et al., 2009). The main attractions for tourists visiting the Indonesian village of Blimbingsari Tourism Village in Bali are the plantation village nearby, the village's uniqueness, the availability of local tour guides, and the service bureau, lodging options, life rural community activities, and rural community engagement (Junaedi and Utama, 2016). It should be possible to get one-stop business advice services for rural businesses, both now and in the future. These services ought to comprise the following: 1) Assessing entrepreneurial skills and aptitudes; 2) Assisting local communities in starting businesses by offering support with legal documentation and registration, drafting business plans, securing funding, and categorizing required training; and 3) Introducing quality standards and forming the Countryside and Agro-Tourism Association (ADB, 2021).

Creating a Fund to Support Rural and Agrotourism

Establishing rules for financing the expansion of rural and agrotourism, and offering rewards for corporate social responsibility (CSR) projects that support rural development and should be evaluated in the tourism sector. Encouraging the funding of programs for the promotion of rural tourism through SME banks or RD and agriculture banks at the same time (ADB, 2021). The government and the weak local communities are also necessary for the long-term survival of Bali Island's tourist village Blimbingsari, as just a fraction of the villagers work in these establishments (Junaedi and Utama, 2016).

Bringing in Both Local and Foreign Capital

The government provides advantageous policies and incentives to investors in the agrotourism sector. Both domestic and foreign investors that want to invest in remote and rural areas will receive incentives through the enactment of laws and regulations that are realistic and supportive of the tourism industry (Khanal & Shrestha, 2019). Agro-tourism in Nepal has the potential to be a novel way to boost income while encouraging farming communities and enthusiastic youth to cultivate crops sustainably by utilizing traditional knowledge, safeguarding biodiversity, and preserving the rural and farming way of life (Maharjan and Dangol, 2018).

CONCLUSION

Based on the result of the article review we observed the agricultural sector is the main sector for Cambodian economic growth. Agricultural sector provided jobs many people in rural areas and most of them are farmers. Farming activities are really attractive to tourists for seeing the plantation, education, entertainment, recreation, and relaxation which link to agriculture. Cambodia has many potential tourisms such as social tourism, ecotourism, natural tourism, and cultural tourism. Those types of tourism are linked to agro-tourism activities such as hospitalities, accommodations, services, agricultural product supplies, food, souvenir gifts, and joining farming activities that lead to increase income for people in rural areas and make a better livelihood. Therefore, The Cambodian government has a high perspective to promote and strategies to foster the agro-tourism sector in the country through the national development policy accordingly.

The political stability provides safety to domestic and international tourists for enjoying their time in Cambodia. Through the stability of politics in the Country is a great opportunity to develop the social infrastructure such as land road, railway, waterway, airway or airport and accommodation facilities. The good infrastructure connects the tourists to all agricultural communities. However, the strategies still remain necessary to monitor the activities of implementation in agro-tourism. On the other hand, the promoting materials is also foster tourist to involve and get clear information in involving in specific area. Encouraging the participation of rural communities in the agro-tourism sector led to quality of modernization and diversification for stability of produce and services. Funding policy is the crucial factor to keep the stability of

rural communities on agricultural business and enterprise and the attraction of investors are a part of development agro-tourism for future stability in rural areas or agricultural communities. The applied national strategies are the main elements for supporting of the agro-tourism sector in Cambodia.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on the topic "Agro-Tourism Development in Cambodia: A Literature Review."

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